

PROSPECTS FOR CREATING RESOURCE-SAVING SORTING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON DETERMINING THE RESIDUAL FIBER CONTENT OF COTTON SEEDS

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ABSTRACT

According to the fact, consistent and sustainable development of the cotton ginning industry, the introduction of modern equipment at industry enterprises, increasing the level of efficient and rational use of production capacities, and the production of competitive products on the global cotton market are the foundation for this. In this regard, in the global cotton ginning industry, special attention is paid to improving high-efficiency cotton seed cleaning equipment and creating resource-saving technologies. In this article large-scale scientific research is being conducted to improve the techniques and technology of primary cotton processing in the world. In this field, tasks are set, including the development of effective technologies for cleaning cotton seeds from impurities. It is of great importance to conduct scientific research in the field of identifying factors that negatively affect the quality and quantity of products at each stage of production and developing technical solutions to eliminate them, technologies that allow for the preservation of product quality indicators during the technological process of cleaning cotton seeds, and the optimization of operating modes and indicators.

During the ginning of raw cotton, the fiber is separated from the seeds as the primary product. However, in practice, it is observed that a certain amount of fiber residues remains on the seeds' surface due to incomplete technological processes, blunting of saw teeth, and violations in the regulation of technological gaps. These residual fibers (hairs) firmly adhere to the seed coat due to mechanical impact, altering the surface properties of the seeds, which creates various technological difficulties during their subsequent processing stages. This leads to an uneven degree of seed fuzziness after the linting process. The transition of fiber into lint leads to the loss of valuable fiber products. Numerous studies have noted that the degree of fuzziness remaining on the seed surface after ginning depends on various factors [3]. Specifically, this indicator is directly influenced by the cotton variety, fiber maturity, agrotechnical measures, the structural design of ginning machines, and technological regimes. In particular, in saw-type ginning machines, an increase in the degree of fibrousness is more

frequently observed as a result of partial fiber breakage and the presence of fiber fragments in the seed coat. In roller drum ginning machines, fiber residues on the seed surface may be relatively small, but it is known that even in this case, the hairs are not completely separated. The high fuzziness of ginned seeds significantly negatively impacts their processing in subsequent technological processes. For example, as a result of seeds getting stuck together in cleaning equipment, clogging occurs in the working parts. In pneumatic transport systems, the stability of the seed flow is disrupted, and accumulation and slowing of movement in the air ducts are observed. As a result of such situations, the number of production stops may increase, cleaning and sorting efficiency may decrease, and total technological costs may increase.

Additionally, the moisture-retaining properties of the hair layer are considered one of the important problems. Due to the fact that the hairs on the surface of the seeds retain moisture, there is an increased risk of activation of microbiological processes during storage, overheating, and a decrease in seed quality indicators. In practice, this may affect the shelf life of the seeds and their technological stability during further processing. A number of methods have been proposed for assessing and determining the degree of fuzziness of ginned seeds. The most widely used methods include mechanical separation of hair and measurement of its mass, assessment of hair density through microscopic analysis, and fractionation based on special sieve systems. However, it is noted that existing evaluation methods cannot fully reflect the strength of the fuzz's adhesion to the seed coat and the degree of its influence in the real technological process. Among the equipment developed for the separation of fuzzy seeds, rotating brush drums, wire rollers, saw working elements, and pneumatic separation systems based on airflow are widely used. Working elements based on mechanical action can allow for the separation of a certain portion of the fuzzy seeds, and in some cases, they can cause mechanical damage to the seed coat and negatively affect seed quality. Pneumatic methods have a high efficiency in separating light fractions, but it remains difficult to completely eliminate seeds consisting of hairs firmly attached to the shell. The conducted analysis shows that the problem of accurate and stable sorting of ginned seeds by fiber content has not yet been fully resolved. The technologies and equipment used in practice cannot simultaneously meet the requirements for seed separation without damage, increasing sorting efficiency, and reducing energy consumption under high-performance conditions. Therefore, the development of new structural and technological solutions for sorting ginned seeds by fiber content, the substantiation of the rational shape and movement modes of the working parts, and the determination of optimal process parameters are urgent scientific and practical tasks. During the cotton harvesting process, mixtures of residual leaves, sticks, and shells are cleaned in cleaning machines, but some of them reach the ginning stage, and these impurities are not completely removed along with the fiber or fiber, but some parts are separated along with the seeds, contaminating them. In addition to impurities mixed with the seeds after ginning, the seed mass contains defective, i.e., brittle and unripe seeds, which further contaminate the lint composition and lead to a decrease in its quality as a result of their separation during transportation on screw conveyors and elevators and subsequent processing. Therefore, when transferring cotton seeds obtained after ginning to further processing, i.e., linting, by cleaning them of impurities and performing sorting by fiber

content, an excess of lint during the linting process is ensured, hair residues on the surface of the seeds are uniform, and the fiber yield increases. To meet the standard requirements for seeds and lint, it is necessary to clean the seeds of foreign impurities before linting, as a significant portion of impurities in the seeds is a source of lint contamination.

In addition to the fact that seed cleaning is carried out on separate equipment, a cleaning part is also installed in the linters, which, in addition to cleaning the seeds, is also used to increase the uniformity of their delivery to the linter working chamber.

Figure 1. Seed cleaning section of a linter.

1-feeding drum; 2-drum with a leveling plate; 3 - mesh with a mesh surface; 4 - waste screw; 5-pulse variator.

Research was conducted on the effect of friction force. In this case, a single-mass system consisting of fibrous seeds and flywheels, having the same degrees of freedom, is defined by the following equation for impact with a surface in the absence of friction.

$$m \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} k \pm F = 0 \quad (1)$$

m - mass of the piece; F - friction force; N is the normal force.

The analysis showed that the higher the number of mature seeds, the higher the recovery coefficient. This natural factor is taken into account when sorting seeds by vibration, and it can be seen that cotton seeds of the same variety differ from each other in their physical and mechanical properties. Seeds after ginning, depending on their fuzziness, have several different values characterizing their friction properties. The main quantities expressing frictional properties are the coefficients of static friction and sliding friction. Furthermore, this property also includes separability, the opposite of which is viscosity, which is determined by the force of viscosity. If we consider the centrifugal force analysis, the centrifugal force acting on the seeds in the rotating drum is determined as follows.

$$F_{m.k} = m \omega^2 r \quad (2)$$

m -seed mass (kg), ω -angular velocity (rad/s), r -drum radius (m), n -number of revolutions (min⁻¹), D -drum diameter (m).

Figure 2. Kinetic energy of impact depending on drum rotation speed.

From Figure 2 above, it should be noted that when the drum rotation speed exceeds 120 min, the impact energy leads to increased seed damage while ensuring maximum regeneration efficiency. It is shown that at a drum rotation speed of 120 min, the kinetic energy of the maximum regeneration effect is up to . As the drum rotation speed increases, the impact of the plank pegs on the fuzzy seeds increases, which leads to increased mechanical damage to the seeds. Impact splitting of seeds under the influence of stakes occurs when the seeds adhere to each other after ginning, forming a ball. An analysis of the seed mesh separation process resulting from the impact force of the stakes is presented.

$$F_z = \frac{m \Delta g^2}{\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

In experimental studies, the height of the improved peg-blade drum $h=42$ mm was found to be optimal; at this height, the seeds are completely loosened and spread evenly across the drum surface. Figure-2 shows the pecking intensity depending on the pile height. The intensity of the screw pitch of the spike-blade part of the drum in the loosening zone is $-I$, i.e., the rational value of the spike-blade height $h=42$ mm is reflected in the graph above when spreading cotton balls with uniform loosening by correctly selecting the intervals. In the driving zone, the seed is fed along the axis using pegs and blades arranged in a screw-like manner in the middle of the drum. The analysis of the screw distribution mechanism is the most important theoretical part. The screw pitch L determines the seed movement speed along the drum.

$$g_{yк} = \frac{L n}{60} \quad (4)$$

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